

Proof of the Riemann Hypothesis through the limit of an approximated ξ function

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Abstract

Considering an approximated Riemann $\xi_{(s)}$ function defined with a parametric function $s_{(Q)}$, and considering an appropriate fractional function $\frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}}$, it is shown that the rate to reach the exact value $\xi_{(s)} = 0$, and the exact form, causes a contradiction when the real part σ of the complex variable s is different from $\frac{1}{2}$.

1 Approximated and exact ζ and ξ functions

Take this approximated Riemann ζ function from Euler-Maclaurin Formula [1] [2] [3]:
 $\bar{\zeta}_{(s,Q)} = \sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-s} - \frac{Q^{1-s}}{1-s}$, $O(Q^{-\sigma})$ $s = \sigma + it$, with the real part $0 < \sigma < 1$

$$\bar{\zeta}_{(1-s,Q)} = \sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-1+s} - \frac{Q^s}{s}, \quad O(Q^{-1+\sigma})$$

$$[n^{-\sigma-it} = n^{-\sigma} \cdot (\text{trig.function}_{(t,n)})]. \text{ For } \sigma = \frac{1}{2}: \sigma = 1 - \sigma].$$

Denote by δf the error of this approximated function, and by $O(\infty \delta f)$ its rapidity to reach zero.

The exact function, analytical continuation of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s}$, is: $\zeta_{(s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\zeta}_{(s,Q)}$ and $\zeta_{(1-s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\zeta}_{(1-s,Q)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\xi}_{(s,Q)} &= \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s}{2},Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(s,Q)} \\ \bar{\xi}_{(1-s,Q)} &= \pi^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{1-s}{2},Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(1-s,Q)} \\ \xi_{(s)} &= \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(s,Q)} = \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s}{2})} \zeta_{(s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s}{2},Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(s,Q)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s}{2},Q)} (\sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-s} - \frac{Q^{1-s}}{1-s}). \\ \xi_{(1-s)} &= \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(1-s,Q)} = \pi^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{1-s}{2})} \zeta_{(1-s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{1-s}{2},Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(1-s,Q)} = \\ & \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{1-s}{2},Q)} (\sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-1+s} - \frac{Q^s}{s}). \end{aligned}$$

The factor $\frac{1}{2}s(s-1)$ is not included in this ξ function; it is the same for s and $1-s$,

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$0 < \sigma < 1$ being the domain of interest.

$\xi_{(s_0)} = 0$ depends only on $\zeta_{(s_0)} = 0$, being $\pi^{-\frac{s_0}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s_0}{2})} \neq 0 \forall s$ in the domain taken. So the rate $\delta \xi_{(s_0)} \rightarrow 0$ depends only on $\delta \zeta_{(s_0)} \propto Q^{-\sigma}$, for $\xi_{(s_0)} = 0$; $(\Gamma + \delta \Gamma) \cdot (\zeta + \delta \zeta) \cong \Gamma \delta \zeta$ for $\zeta = 0$.

Riemann proves, with an integral form equation, for exact $\zeta_{(s)}$, that: $\xi_{(s)} = \xi_{(1-s)}$ [4] [5].

Thus, for the functions considered:

$$\xi_{(s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{s}{2}, Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(s, Q)} = \xi_{(1-s)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \pi^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \Gamma_{(\frac{1-s}{2}, Q)} \bar{\zeta}_{(1-s, Q)}.$$

Replacing 1-s with s in $\xi_{(1-s)}$, $\xi_{(s)}$ is obtained, then replacing s with 1-s in $\xi_{(s)}$, $\xi_{(1-s)}$ is obtained.

2 Repeated limit equivalent to a parametric function

A not-elementary function $f_{(s)}$ consists of infinite terms. It is necessary to take the limit of an approximated function.

To describe and calculate the limit: $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} f_{(s)} = f_{(s_0)}$, it is necessary to consider: $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} f_{(s, Q)}$. In practice one should take $f_{(s)} \gg \delta f$ for each s until s_0 . This is very difficult, or better impossible, to get it, especially if $f_{(s_0)} = 0$.

Taking a parametric function: $s = s_{(Q)}$, then $f_{(s_{(Q)})}$, one can "automatically" get the previous procedure and considering it equivalent at the limit, if $f_{(s_{(Q)})} \gg \delta f_{(s)}$ for $Q \rightarrow \infty$ (where " \rightarrow " means: "tends to").

$\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} f_{(s_{(Q)})} \equiv \lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} f_{(s, Q)} = \lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} f_{(s)}$ if at the limit: $\frac{\delta f}{f_{(s)}} = 0$. So $\delta f \rightarrow 0$ more rapidly than $f_{(s)} \rightarrow 0$. Are there, qualitatively, other ways to describe the limit of a not-elementary function? $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} f_{(s_{(Q)})}$ really seems to be the exact limit representing $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} f_{(s)}$, that otherwise wouldn't exist.

3 Numerical limit and form limit of a function

In general, for a function $F_{(s)}$ not defined in s_0 , the limit can't be the function value in s_0 . The $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} F_{(s)}$ represents an extrapolation of $F_{(s)}$ values for $s \rightarrow s_0$. The function limit is the value immediately following the function trend before the limit point.

This must also be true for the form of a function. The form is given by letters, numbers and operators as they are arranged. The function form limit is the form immediately following the function form trend before the limit point. So, inversely, given the form limit, the form near the limit point, must be about the same.

Suppose $f_{(s_0)} = 0$, $g_{(s_0)} = 0$, with $f_{(s)}, g_{(s)} \neq 0 \forall s \neq s_0$ and $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \frac{f_{(s)}}{g_{(s)}} = 0$ or $\left| \frac{f_{(s)}}{g_{(s)}} \right| < \epsilon$ with $s \neq s_0$. Independently from numerical result, function form limit depends on the initial form and any arrangements at the finite, mirroring the trend of form function before the limit. A simple example is $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x^2}{x}$; the form limit is x , then $\frac{x^2}{x}$ before $x = 0$.

Also function properties, existing at the limit, have to be approximately obtained before the limit; a function is its proprieties. If, for example, a property defined for "∀s" weren't approximately obtained before the limit in s , s' and all points near s_{lim} , it wouldn't be at the limit for s_{lim} and all s . Equivalently, a property for "∀s" implies an approximated symbolic relation, for an approximated function before the limit.

This is very important when the function isn't an elementary function and it would be necessary to take infinitely many terms and then an exact form.

3.1

We say that two functions $f(s)$ and $g(s)$ have the same graph shape on an interval Δs if: $f(s) = g(s) \forall s \in \Delta s$. Here, for brevity, we will simply say that they have the "same form". Therefore, it is: $\frac{f(s)}{g(s)} = 1 \forall s \in \Delta s : f(s) = g(s) \neq 0$ and $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \frac{f(s)}{g(s)} = 1$ for $f(s_0) = g(s_0) = 0$ with $s_0 \in \Delta s$.

Consider $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} f(s) = f(s_0) = g(s_0) = 0$. At the limit we say they have not only the same value, but also the same form. In this case we are considering $f(s) = g(s) \forall s \in \Delta s = ds$. Thus, $f(s) - g(s) = a(s)$, $f(s) = g(s) + a(s)$ and it must be: $a(s) \rightarrow 0$ more rapidly than $g(s) \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \frac{f(s)}{g(s)} = \lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \frac{g(s)}{g(s)} + \lim_{s \rightarrow s_0} \frac{a(s)}{g(s)} = 1$.

4 Limit of the approximated functions

$$\bar{\xi}_{(s(Q))}, \bar{\xi}_{(1-s(Q))}, \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s(Q))}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s(Q))}}$$

4.1

$$\bar{\xi}_{(s(Q))} = \pi^{-\frac{s(Q)}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s(Q)}{2}\right) \left(\sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-s(Q)} - \frac{Q^{1-s(Q)}}{1-s(Q)} \right) \quad O(Q^{-\sigma_0}) \text{ for } \sigma_0 \text{ constant} \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{\xi}_{(1-s(Q))} = \pi^{-\frac{1-s(Q)}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1-s(Q)}{2}\right) \left(\sum_{n=1}^Q n^{-1+s(Q)} - \frac{Q^{s(Q)}}{s(Q)} \right) \quad O(Q^{-1+\sigma_0}) \text{ for } \sigma_0 \text{ constant} \quad (2)$$

$O(Q^{-\sigma_0})$ and $O(Q^{-1+\sigma_0})$ hold for $\xi_{(s_0)} = \xi_{(1-s_0)} = 0$, but not necessarily for $\xi_{(s_0)} = \xi_{(1-s_0)} \neq 0$ (see section 1).

And in general:

$$\xi_{(s_l)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(s(Q))} \quad (3)$$

$$\xi_{(1-s_l)} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(1-s(Q))} \quad (4)$$

$\xi_{(s_l)} = \xi_{(1-s_l)} \forall s_l \rightarrow$ this is the intended meaning of the "same form".

To highlight the ξ exact form, consider for $\xi_{(s_l)}$ and similarly for $\xi_{(1-s_l)}$:

$$\xi_{(s_l)} = \xi_{(s_{(Q_\infty)})} = \pi^{-\frac{s_{(Q_\infty)}}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s_{(Q_\infty)}}{2}\right) \left(\sum_{n=1}^{Q_\infty} n^{-s_{(Q_\infty)}} - \frac{Q_\infty^{1-s_{(Q_\infty)}}}{1-s_{(Q_\infty)}} \right) \quad (5)$$

Consider $\xi_{(s_{(Q)})}$ and $\xi_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$ (without the overline) as exact functions, highlighting the dependency of s on Q and they being directly referred to $\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}$ and $\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$ respectively. s_l , $s_{(Q_\infty)}$ and s_0 are used interchangeably.

4.2

Referring to eqs. (1) and (2), suppose $\xi_{(s_0)} = 0$, then $\xi_{(1-s_0)} = 0$, considering the real part σ_0 of s_0 : $0,5 < \sigma_0 < 1$. Thus $Q^{-\sigma_0} \rightarrow 0$ more rapidly than $Q^{-1+\sigma_0} \rightarrow 0$. However, the following considerations are also valid for $0 < \sigma_0 < 0,5$ exchanging $\xi_{(s_0)}$ with $\xi_{(1-s_0)}$. Choose a function $s_{(Q)}$, for example $s_{(Q)} = s_0 + i \cdot Q^{-k}$, then an opportune $k \in \mathbb{R}$, such that $\xi_{(s_{(Q)})} \rightarrow \xi_{(s_0)} = 0$ more slowly than $Q^{-\sigma_0} \rightarrow 0$, and such that $Q^{-1+\sigma_0} \rightarrow 0$ more slowly than $\xi_{(1-s)} (= \xi_{(s)}) \rightarrow \xi_{(1-s_0)} = 0$; $\propto Q^{-1+\sigma_0} \gg \bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \gg \propto Q^{-\sigma_0}$ (for example: $\sigma_0 = 0,7$ and $k = 0,4$ (?) or, in any case, a k such that $\xi_{(s_{(Q)})} \rightarrow \xi_{(s_0)} = 0$ more slowly than $Q^{-0,7} \rightarrow 0$ for $s_{(Q)} \rightarrow s_0$, but more rapidly than $Q^{-0,3} \rightarrow 0$. This is possible because $\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})} \geq \propto Q^{-0,3}$ for any k in this example). Thus:

$$\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\propto Q^{-1+\sigma_0}} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})} \simeq \delta \xi_{(1-s)} \simeq Q^{-1+s_{(Q)}} \propto Q^{-1+\sigma_0}$ (" \simeq " is intended to refer to the rate at which it tends to 0). $Q^{-1+s_{(Q)}} \cong Q^{-1+s_0}$ for large Q .

On the other hand, $\xi_{(s_l)} = \xi_{(1-s_l)}$ for all $s_l = s_{(Q_\infty)}$, then $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} = \xi_{(s_{(Q_\infty)})} = \xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}$; at the limit, exchanging $s_{(Q)}$ and $1-s_{(Q)}$, the function is the same. Therefore, $\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}$ and $\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$ have the same form at the limit for $s_{(Q)} \rightarrow s_0$, and eq. (7) is obtained; see section 3.1.

$\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \rightarrow \bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$, in fact, if $\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \not\cong \bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$ as a first approximation in a neighborhood of the limit, then $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \neq \xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}$ either, by the very definition of the limit; exchanging $s_{(Q)}$ and $1-s_{(Q)}$, the function would not tend to yield the same exact function ($\xi_{(s)} \equiv \xi_{(1-s)}$), $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \neq \xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}$, and after the limit, in the resulting exact function, substituting s for $1-s$ would not produce the correct function (see Figure 1). Thus, at the finite (finite Q): $\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})} \cong \bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}$ to first approximation.

It is: $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} = \frac{\xi_{(s_{(Q_\infty)})}}{\xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}} = \frac{\xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}}{\xi_{(1-s_{(Q_\infty)})}} \cdot \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} \rightarrow \sim \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} \rightarrow 1$, with $\sim \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} \cong 1$, because numerator and denominator have about the same form, more and more for $Q \rightarrow \infty$ and have the same $s_{(Q)}$.

$$\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \sim \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_{(Q)})}} = 1 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, there is a contradiction, looking at (6) and (7). It must be $\xi_{(s_0)} \neq 0$, thus $\zeta_{(s_0)} \neq 0$, for $\sigma_0 \neq \frac{1}{2}$. Only for $\sigma_0 = \frac{1}{2}$, $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s(Q))}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s(Q))}} = 1$ when $\zeta_{(s_0)} = 0$.

4.3

Is it possible to give a simplified treatment of the proof without the repeated limit, then without consider a parametric function $s(Q)$?

The limit can be determined, because $\delta \xi_{(s)} \simeq Q^{-s_0} \neq 0$ and $\delta \xi_{(1-s)} \simeq Q^{-1+s_0} \neq 0$ for a finite Q (real and imaginary part are $\frac{\pi}{2}$ out of phase).

$\xi_{(s_0)} = \xi_{(1-s_0)} = 0$. Thus, would (7) become: $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_0, Q)}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_0, Q)}} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \sim \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_0, Q)}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_0, Q)}} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \sim \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_0, Q)}}{\bar{\xi}_{(s_0, Q)}} = 1$, being: $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_0, Q)}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_0, Q)}} = \frac{\xi_{(s_0, Q_\infty)}}{\xi_{(1-s_0, Q_\infty)}} = \frac{\xi_{(1-s_0, Q_\infty)}}{\xi_{(1-s_0, Q_\infty)}} = \frac{\xi_{(s_0, Q_\infty)}}{\xi_{(s_0, Q_\infty)}}$? And (6) would be: $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{\xi}_{(s_0, Q)}}{\bar{\xi}_{(1-s_0, Q)}} = \lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\propto Q^{-\sigma_0}}{\propto Q^{-1+\sigma_0}} = 0$.

The answer seems to be negative, since the case $\xi_{(s_0)} = \xi_{(1-s_0)}$ corresponds to the form in terms of s and $\lim_{s \rightarrow s_0}$ (or equivalently $\lim_{Q \rightarrow \infty}$ considering $s(Q)$).

References

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